

Synaptic Sanctum Neuroscape: real-time emotionally adaptive music in a VR immersive environment

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

Synaptic Sanctum Neuroscape is an immersive EEG-driven project that intertwines the realms of neuroscience, music composition, and VR. Developed using Max/MSP and UE5, this immersive experience employs a custom EEG device to read users' brainwaves, transforming their neural activity into emotionally adaptive music and particle systems. The sound spatialization is managed by the IRCAM's Spat5 ambisonics library, and music and environmental sounds are rendered in binaural format for the VR headset's headphones, allowing for a 3D perception of the music and enhancing the overall sense of presence and engagement.

In a surreal and dark landscape scattered with ancient ruins of a decayed past, the user strolls on a thirsty land generating music in real-time with their brainwaves and emotional response; reflecting the user's alert/relaxed states and adapting the musical landscape in response to the evolving emotional dynamics, the auditory experience becomes an intimate collaboration between their neural patterns and the generative musical algorithm. The EEG data also drives particle systems, and manages the duration of a 3D granulator's grains which manifests as glowing spheres within the virtual space utilizing concatenative synthesis where each sphere encapsulates a unique sonic fragment, and its position and size are given by its sonic features.

Fig. 1. Particle system, EEG data, head tracking in Spat5.

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2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The custom EEG sensor is built using a BITalino EEG chip, a self-soldered voltage divider, and an Arduino Uno board; the EEG chip is a bipolar single-channel sensor that gets its data through medical adhesive disposable patches; the positive and negative poles are placed on the forehead or the temples, and neutral behind the right ear. The EEG sensor captures the user's brainwave activity by measuring the potential difference detected between the two poles (positive and negative) of the electrodes. The detected gain is $\pm 39.49\mu\text{V}$ (with $VCC = 3.3\text{V}$) with a bandwidth of 0.8 to 48Hz [1], and Arduino reads an ADC input that corresponds to 1.8 to 5.5V in the analog domain. The data is received via Bluetooth by Max/MSP where it is first smoothed to get rid of any unwanted peak generated by other electromagnetic sources, and then processed via FFT analysis to extract the frequency range of each brainwave.

Fig. 3. Brainwaves' FFT analysis with 16th order Butterworth bandpass filters.

Once the brainwave activity is correctly detected, it is then mapped and sent to the sonification subpatches in Max/MSP and to UE5 via OSC. In normal awake brain activity, Alpha, Beta, and Gamma brainwaves are commonly observed: Alpha waves are generally associated with memory and mental activity, but they can also be triggered by closed-eyes meditation and rest; Beta waves are generated by the normal alert state, active thinking, and concentration, and they are also triggered by visual and sound stimuli; Gamma waves are the fastest brainwaves and are related to high brain activity and audio-visual stimuli synthesis [2].

The brainwave activity is then used to trigger sound gestures and drive sound generators. The activity is smoothed and used in various ways in Max/MSP such as envelope generator, pitch, time, and timbre modulator, or as a quasi-random generator for complex patches featuring a series of functions, mappings, and envelopes. It is also used to drive particle systems in UE5. Additionally, there are pre-decided thresholds whose crossing triggers various events such as gate aperture, delay triggering, note triggering in Max, and light dimming in UE5. The overall aim of the mapping is to generate music and visuals that are organic to the

user's emotional state, with rhythm and pitch slowing down during states of relaxation, and increasing during periods of heightened alertness. As an example, here, based on the relaxation or alertness state, a polyrhythm is going to change in rate and pitch, as well as the granulator's grains duration. The resulting musical composition becomes a dynamic mirror of our unique neural activity, offering a nuanced artistic representation of our emotional responses and demonstrating that technology can be a tool for self-discovery and expression.

The brainwaves' activity data is then packed in an OSC bundle and sent over UDP to UE5; with the OSC plugin enabled, the OSC bundle is received, and each message is unpacked and further processed to be mapped to any mappable parameter inside UE5. As an example, the gamma threshold is mapped to turn a light on and off, and the gamma values drive a particle system's noise strength.

The granulator is created in Max/MSP using the MuBu-CataRT library for concatenative synthesis. The audio samples are automatically opened at patch start, and their features (CentroidMean, PeriodicityMean, FrequencyMean) are sent via OSC to UE5 where they are collected into arrays (X, Y, size), mapped, scaled, and used for the 3D granulator construction.

Fig. 4. 3D granulator in UE5 and Max/MSP.

The user's global position in UE5 is then sent back to Max/MSP, mapped, scaled, and normalized, to drive the position in the granulator. The spatialization of the sound grains is directly managed by the IRCAM's Spat5 ambisonics library and is based on the grains' position.

Spat5 also handles the emotionally adaptive music's spatialization using the VR headset rotation. The HMD coordinates are gathered in Max and UE5 separately, in order to avoid any delay: UE5 gathers them automatically, while Max needs the Graham Wakefield's VR library. The head tracking coordinates and the head rotation quaternion are extracted from the VR object. The YPR¹ are organized

¹ Yaw, pitch, roll.

differently in Oculus and in Spat, thus, in order to have the right rotation axes mapped to Spat, they have to be converted from XYZ in Oculus space to YZX in Spat space.

Fig. 5. Oculus head tracking coordinates and rotations. In “Head tracking for the Oculus Rift”, LaValle et al. Fig. 6. Spat head tracking coordinates and rotations. In “Spatialisateur user manual”, Carpentier.

They are then fed into the Spat operator and used to place the VR headset’s headphones in the middle of the 3D sound space. The operator, together with the user’s head orientation, also handles the sound sources’ position and panning. Everything is then decoded in binaural format with an IRC_1040 HRTF.

Fig. 7. Connections.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

This VR installation only requires a chair for the user to sit on and a table to host the gaming laptop to where the EEG device and the VR headset are connected. The author will bring the laptop with everything already installed and ready to go, and the EEG device with the disposable patches. It would be ideal if NIME could provide the VR headset, but if it's not possible the author can bring theirs. An Oculus Rift has been used for development, but the work can be tested on a wide array of other headsets. Being a VR installation, the fruition is just for one user at a time, but potentially it could be set up with a screen or projector, and with a loudspeaker array, so as to have a larger audience enjoying it. NIME will need to provide the screen/projector, the speakers, and the audio device for this setup. If the project is chosen, we can further discuss the available options. Time will be 2 hours top for the simple VR installation, while VR + speaker array will probably take 6-8 hours.

Regarding the space, it depends on the decided format, but a dedicated quiet space would be best, so the users can calmly be immersed in the sound of their mind.

ETHICAL STANDARDS

The project has been created respecting Abertay University's ethical standards. The user's physiological data gathered during the installation are not being recorded or used in any other way than the art generation during the use, and are not going to be stored anywhere.

Furthermore, I want to emphasize that the project has been developed with no funding of any sort, and the choice for the EEG device's components has been driven by the will to create the cheapest EEG device possible that can be built by anyone with less than £50. Unreal Engine 5 is free to download and use, Max/MSP has a free full demo period of 30 days, past which saving gets disabled, while the Max libraries used are completely free to download.

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